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SPECULATION OPPORTUNITIES IN DERIVATIVES TOWARDS FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT

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ABSTRACT

Speculation is one of the instruments in derivatives for booking significant profit with high risk in certain period of time. The FDI is playing vital role in our country's economic growth and it is providing huge contribution to volatility in derivatives. The present study analysed speculation opportunities in derivatives towards FDI. This study found that out of seven hypotheses, five hypotheses showed significant "t" values and two hypotheses did not proved significant relation between variables. Finally, the study concluded that volatility is suitable key factor for speculation to high risk traders.

Key Words: FDI, Derivatives, Volatility, Speculation, Correlation co-efficient, "t" value.

Introduction:

Developing countries always need financial support to achieve their stability in economy. Similarly, India being developing country is looking forward for foreign direct investment to move in a direction to become a developed economy. We all know that Indian economy is a fast growing economy and it holds highly strong position in global hub as Indian economy registers high growth figures of economy when globally there was a heavy financial meltdown. Due to this growth, investors of overseas are confident and interested to invest in India which is accepting overseas investment and boost our strengthen economy policy to achieve goals.

FDI is major source of external finance to domestic country. It is giving an enormous contribution for gear up and steadfast to domestic economical growth through improve and restructure of domestic infrastructure, increased better human resource, in an effort to increase productivity, reduce unemployment etc., in mean while stock market also play an inevitable role to increase domestic revenue by their commission. Speculation is one of the key factors to revenue heap up of the market.

FDI is consider as much more stable than FII inflow because FDI brings not just capital but also better technology, management and also governance practices. Especially the know-how or the technology that gets transferred along with FDI is often more crucial and significant than the capital itself. Direct investment in order to create or increase capacity ensures that the capital inflow gets translated into augmented production. In the case of FII investment that flows into the stock market, the effect is to increase capital availability in general, rather than availability of capital with a particular Company.ⁱ

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT

Definition of **FDI** is direct investments in productive assets by a company incorporated in a foreign country, as opposed to investment in shares of local companies by foreign entities. The investing company may make its overseas investment in a number of ways – either by setting up a subsidiary or associate company in the foreign country, by acquiring shares of an overseas company, or through a merger or joint venture.ⁱⁱ

DERIVATIVES

The term 'Derivative' stands for a contract whose price is derived from or is dependent upon an underlying asset. A security whose price is dependent upon or derived from one or more underlying assets, the

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derivatives itself is merely a contract between two or more parties. Its value is determined by fluctuations in the underlying asset. The most common underlying assets include stocks, bonds, commodities, currencies, interest rates and market indexes. Most derivatives are characterized by high leverage. Derivatives are generally used as an instrument to hedge risk, but can also be used for speculative purposes.

SPECULATION

Speculation involves trading a financial instrument involving high risk, in expectation of significant returns. The motive is to take maximum advantage from fluctuations in the market.

SPECULATORS

The Commodity Futures Trading Commission in the US (“CFTC”) defines a speculator as: “a trader who does not hedge, but who trades with the objective of achieving profits through the successful anticipation or price movements”.ⁱⁱⁱ

These are individuals who take a view on the future direction of the markets. They take a view whether prices would rise or fall in future and accordingly buy or sell futures and options to try and make a profit from the future price movements of the underlying asset.^{iv}

IMPORTANCE OF FDI TO OUR COUNTRY

Our Growing economy needs plenty foreign capital in the form of FDI & FII for the development of basic infrastructure like Roads, Railways, Sea Ports, Warehouses, Banking and insurance services and Retail etc. Moreover, rapid industrialization since 1991 has further strengthened the need of foreign capital across various industries. Many developing countries suffer from severe scarcity of funds in highly capital intensive areas such as infrastructure. This problem can be diverted to the foreign capitalists by allowing them to invest. The variations in the cost of capital are also one of the important factors resulting in attracting foreign capital in India. Example; Interest rates are high in India as compared to developed economies. In several countries the interest rates are as low as 1% to 3%, where as in some countries like India the interest rates are very high as 8% to 10% per annum. Thus FDI acts as a cheap source of foreign capital. It also helps in supplementing domestic savings and investments. It also leads to higher asset prices in the Indian market.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

In before that 1991, the common man said, “stock market is gambling, speculation is very bad word”, but, the new epoch was started in financial market by reformation of Indian economy by relaxation of Foreign direct investment. In mean while the world economy disclosed the new track to hedge, risk diversification, leverage for highest profit booking to traders and Wall Street often blamed for our current economy issues. Often we fail to recognize in that speculators contribute huge liquidity to our financial market. Apart from this the speculation trading is indirectly generates employment opportunities for around 15.3 lakh personals and further observes that contribution of the derivatives market turnover to India’s GDP was around 0.23% in 2010-11. These numbers are expected to increase to 0.33% of GDP and 0.61% of the service sector GDP by 2014-15. The growth of speculative contribution implied that importance of participation of financial instruments in India’s GDP.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present paper makes an attempt to understand and utilization of opportunities of speculation in derivatives market towards FDI flows during the period of 2000 to 2014. It also attempts to find out the correlation relationship between FDI flows on BSE sensx and Nifty by the Karl Pearson’s Coefficient of correlation. This study is important to traders as well as investors for reduce their risk, to take maximum profit with brave mindset.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the speculation opportunities in derivatives towards FDI Flows,
- To find out the decision making on execution of derivatives in market volatility,
- To measure the opportunities utilization behavior during trading from investor’s point of view.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In 1997 **World Bank** has done a study and reported that stock market liquidity improved in those emerging economies that received higher foreign investments.^v **Zhong M. et al., (2004)**, his current discussions also delineate the controversial role of speculators, and recognize the impact of price manipulation and herding behavior on equity markets. His research on the volume-volatility relationship shows that there is a positive correlation between the two. Regarding the role of derivatives, evidence both supports and refutes the argument of market stabilization, while new research areas, such as individual share futures, feedback trading, and volatility futures, are explored.^{vi} **Adam and Anokye et al (2009)** in their study examined the impact of FDI on stock market in Ghana by using multivariate co integration and Innovation Accounting Methods. Their results indicate a long-run relationship between FDI, nominal exchange rate and stock market development in Ghana.^{vii} **Jayachandiran. G and Seilan. A (2010)**, investigated the relationship between trade, foreign direct investment and economic growth of India over the period 1970-2007. The results of Granger causality test showed that there is a causal relationship between the examined variables. The direction of causality relationship is from foreign direct investment to growth rate and there is causality relationship from growth rates to foreign direct investments.^{viii} **Pirrong (2010b)**, explains it as follows, most speculators using futures offset their positions prior to maturity, and hence never make or take delivery of the actual commodity. For instance, a speculator who buys July crude oil futures in January typically sells his contract prior to July. Thus, this speculator never directly affects production or consumption of the physical commodity, so it is difficult to understand exactly how he could affect the price that a consumer pays at the pump or in the grocery.^{ix} **Brunetti, Buyuksahim, and Harris (2011)** study specific categories of traders and test whether positions taken by speculators such as hedge funds and swap dealers cause changes in oil futures prices or price volatility. Their results are consistent with speculators providing valuable liquidity to the market and with speculators reacting to market conditions rather than vice versa.^x **Karl Shutes, Gerdien W. Meijerink (2012)**, an important incidental benefit that flows from derivatives trading is that it acts as a catalyst for new entrepreneurial activity. In the public debate about speculation, it is sometimes posited that the large influx of speculative capital on futures markets has (1) pushed up futures prices artificially and (2) that the link between physical cash prices and futures prices is the other way round: futures prices determine cash prices. (3) Others suggest that the large influx of speculative capital has led to higher price volatility.^{xi} **Thomas Neon (2012)**, disclosure of his study, market always giving an opportunity to trade by smooth out pricing anomalies in correlated markets.^{xii}

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study on this topic has done by adopting survey method of research. It consists of both descriptive and analytical methods of study. Questionnaire was prepared by researcher to find out the speculation opportunities in derivatives towards foreign direct investment from investor's point of view in selected area. The reviews have also been collected from international journals, books, and reports on related subject.

SECONDARY DATA COLLECTION

This study is based on secondary and primary data. The collected secondary data was related to flows of FDI and indices and that volatility. The secondary data have been collected from Nifty and Sensex indices from www.investing.com, DIPP's FDI Data base, and reserve bank of India websites. The study considers 14 years data starting from 2000 to 2014.

PRIMARY DATA COLLECTION

The researcher adopted survey method for collection of primary data from investor's point of view by "5" point Likert Scale" from respondents and samples are collected from Karvy Stock Broking Limited and Geojit Financial services Limited, Vellore. The sample sizes of 80 traders are randomly selected for this study on study period of September 2014 to November 2014.

DATA ANALYSIS

Karl Pearson's co-efficient correlation tool was used for secondary data analysis. Coefficient correlation is a statistical tool that determines the degree to which two variable's movements are associated. The

value of coefficient correlation varies from -1 to +1. Positive value of correlation indicates if one variable increases in its values, the other variable also increases in its values.

Descriptive analyses were used for primary data analysis. The 'r', and 't' values were used for primary data analysis from the 48 suitable questionnaires

SECONDARY DATA ANALYSIS

Correlation is applied to study the statistical relationship of the variables of FDI inflow, FDI outflow and speculation opportunities in CNX Nifty and BSE Sensex. The following table No.:2 present the volatility of the market from 14 years data. The collected data were used for find out the correlation relationship on the result it can be concluded that there is very strong positive correlation between FDI inflows and outflows & CNX Nifty and BSE Sensex indices. Volatility and speculation opportunities correlation is found to be significant at 1 percent level of significance. It reflects when FDI comes into the market, indices were going up and when FDI goes out from market, indices were fell down. It means that there is a positive correlation between FDI inflows and outflows & CNX Nifty and BSE Sensex.

METHOD OF COMPUTATION OF VOLATILITY^{xiii}

The Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) method for calculating volatility places greater emphasis on more recent returns. It is used to obtain the volatility estimate every day. The estimate at the end of day 't', σ_t is estimate using the previous day's volatility estimate σ_{t-1} (as at the end of day t-1), and the return (r_t) observed in the futures market on day t.

$$\text{The EWMA formula is: } (\sigma_t^2) = \lambda (\sigma_{t-1})^2 + (1 - \lambda)(r_t)^2$$

Here is λ a parameter which determines how rapidly volatility estimates change. A value of 0.94 is used for λ . Span uses the risk arrays to scan probable underlying market price changes and probable volatility changes for all contracts in a portfolio, in order to determine value gains and losses at the portfolio level. This is the single most important calculation executed by system.

TABLE NO.:1

KARL PEARSON'S COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION

Volatility	FDI inflow	FDI outflow
CNX Nifty	0.8753	0.3619
BSE Sensex	0.8765	0.3754

CHART No.:1

TABLE NO.:2

SHOWING THE DETAILS OF YEAR WISE FDI INFLOWS AND OUTFLOWS & CNX NIFTY AND BSE SENSEX WITH PERIODICAL HIGH & LOW

Sl. No	Year	FDI (in million US\$)		CNX Nifty*		BSE Sensex*	
		Inflow**	Outflow**	High	Low	High	Low
1	2000-2001	2339	602.12	1636	1098	5542	3436
2	2001-2002	3904	878.83	1207	850	3759	2594
3	2002-2003	2574	1746.28	1153	920	3538	2828
4	2003-2004	2197	1250.01	2014	920	6249	2904
5	2004-2005	3250	1481.97	2183	1292	6954	4227
6	2005-2006	5540	6657.82	3433	1896	11356	6118
7	2006-2007	15585	12062.92	4245	2595	14723	8799
8	2007-2008	34573	15431.51	6357	3617	21206	12425
9	2008-2009	31364	12477.14	5298	2252	17735	7697
10	2009-2010	25606	9392.98	5329	2965	17793	9546
11	2010-2011	21376	9234.58	6338	4786	21108	15960
12	2011-2012	34833	4031.45	5944	4531	19811	15190
13	2012-2013	21825	3856.00	6111	4770	20203	15748
14	2013-2014	18749	3186.00	6730	5119	22467	17448

Sources: *Nifty and Sensex indices from www.investing.com, **As per DIPP's FDI Data base.

CHART NO.:2

SHOWING THE DETAILS OF FDI INFLOWS AND OUTFLOWS MOVEMENT OF CNX NIFTY & BSE SENSEX DURING THE PERIOD FROM FINANCIAL YEAR 2000 TO 2014

PRIMARY DATA ANALYSIS

The data were collected from respondents and descriptively examined by statistical tools such as, 'r' value and "t" test. The analysis, findings and results were describing in the next steps.

As depicted in figure no.:3, the research model that we propose to explain the speculation opportunities in derivatives is based on volatility from investor's point of view.

FIG NO.:1 RESEARCH MODEL

The first set of hypothesis (H1, H2) indicates that volatility of market and speculation opportunities in derivatives depends on FDI flows. This implies that traders confidants towards flows of FDI in derivative speculation. The second set of hypothesis (H3) assumes that traders’ decision making towards execution by their opportunities utilization behavior. The third set of hypothesis (H4) describes that description of execution attitude like Emotional or technical. The fourth set of hypothesis (H5, H6, and H7) indicates that opportunities utilization behavior is determined by technical analysis & market sentiment, peer influences & paid calls, trading experiences & Return anxiety.

RESEARCH PROCESS

In this session, design of questionnaire, pilot and final study will be directly discussed.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Section–I provide a narrative introduction to the study, an explanation of the purpose of the questionnaire and description of speculative opportunities in derivatives. In section–II, in addition measures of the constructs in the Research model several demographic related answers were sought. All questions for measures of the constructs in the section were scaled by “5 point Likert Scale” with anchors from “Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

PILOT STUDIES AND FINAL STUDIES

A pilot study was conducted were 80 investors participated to see where the questionnaire needed to be improved. Comments and suggestions received from the pilot test was used and incorporated into the final

version of the questionnaire for the main study. In the main study 100 questionnaire were sent out with 48 useful responses received for subsequent data analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Based on the responses, we conducted a correlation (r) and (t) analysis. The objective of r and t analysis is to study the strength of correlation and relation between set of two variables measured by correlation of co-efficient and ‘t’ test. In our study, we selected a significant level to be 0.05. Based on 48 questionnaire responses of the 7 hypothesis in the research model only two hypotheses were found to be not significant by the survey data collected the table no.: 3 shows the results of the hypothesis testing.

RESULTS OF HYPOTHESES TESTING

Hypothesis No	statement	‘r’ Value	‘t’ value	Result
1	FDI flows and volatility of market	0.63	1.023	Yes
2	Volatility of market and speculation opportunities in derivatives	0.64	1.243	Yes
3	Decision making and opportunities utilization behavior towards speculation	0.64	1.002	Yes
4	Technical execution and emotional execution.	0.33	1.125	Yes
5	Technical analysis and market sentiment.	0.13	1.685	No
6	Paid calls and peer influence.	0.06	1.723	No
7	Trading experiences and returns anxiety.	0.67	0.960	Yes

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. The respondent’s age and educational qualification factors are play a significant role in anticipation of price movement towards foreign direct investment into the market.
2. The respondent’s stock or indices picking attitude is play a vital role,
3. The respondents are having enough level of risk moderate capability
4. Some respondents are utilizing suitable strategy for speculation,
5. Most of the respondents are taking emotional decision making while trade.

RECOMMANTATIONS

1. Brokers can create an awareness about speculation trade to illiterate pupils,
2. Retail investors should not speculate,
3. Any kind of traders should not invest their borrowing money into the market.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this study is to find out the speculation opportunities in derivatives towards flow of foreign direct investment. Based on secondary data analysis is that volatility indicates positive signal to traders for their significant profit by positive correlation. The results of primary data analysis indicate that regarding the hypothesis, there is strong statistical significant decision making of execution. It means that created their level of confidence in technical execution. That implies traders will possess enormous profit for using suitable strategy. Opportunities utilization behavior is playing an essential role in profit booking in speculation. It’s depends on their soundness of trading strategy related with market sentiment. Trading experiences are reduced their return fear and motivate trading confidents. Crowd behavior and emotional trading is fails to return their oxygen in speculation.

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